

A fuzzy logic based approach to the value of information estimation in optimal control problems under uncertainty with applications to ecological management

Version 1

Description

This is DMP for project "A fuzzy logic based approach to the value of information estimation in optimal control problems under uncertainty with applications to ecological management"

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

A fuzzy logic based approach to the value of information estimation in optimal control problems under uncertainty with applications to ecological management (Nr. lzp-2024/1-0188)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: A fuzzy logic based approach to the value of information estimation in optimal control problems under uncertainty with applications to ecological management

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: A fuzzy logic based approach to the value of information estimation in optimal control problems under uncertainty with applications to ecological management (Nr. lzp-2024/1-0188)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

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4. Templates

Descriptions

A fuzzy logic based approach to the value of information estimation in optimal control problems under uncertainty with applications to ecological management

The aim of this project is to develop a rigorous and systematic framework for the fuzzy modeling of decision-making problems with uncertainties in ecological management applications.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of this project is to develop a rigorous and systematic framework for the fuzzy modeling of decision-making problems with uncertainties in ecological management applications. This includes the solution and qualitative analysis of related optimal control problems, as well as the development of recommendations for decision-makers about acquiring new information. To achieve the aim, specific fuzzy logic based modelling tools will be developed and fuzzy model based optimal control techniques will be developed and applied to pollution control and renewable resource extraction problems.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other researchers interested in fuzzy modeling of decision-making problems with uncertainties in ecological management applications.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

No.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Svetlana Asmuss (0000-0002-9623-2169)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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